

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for System Calibration and System Check

Routine of ALTIS QqQ

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Summary:

The System Calibration routine performs the check of spray stability, calibrate the EM Gain, tunes Q1 and Q3 and calibrates the mass analyzer by using the mass position and resolution of the peaks in the EMRS spectrum.

The System Check routine performs the check of spray stability, EM Gain calibration and mass position and resolution calibration by using the measured EMRS spectrum. If any check fails, the System check routine automatically reruns the calibration process for the failed check.

IMPORTANT

- For optimal performance, calibrate the MS every 1 to 3 months.
- Heated ESI (H-ESI) source interface must be mounted.
- Use a proper calibration solution warmed to room temperature: **Pierce Triple Quadrupole Calibration Solution, extended mass range** (cat. # 88340).
- The system calibration process takes 30 to 50 min.

Set up the syringe pump with calibration solution

1. Turn the instrument to **Standby** mode.
2. Fill in the dedicated 500 µl syringe with **Calibration Solution** and place it into syringe pump.
3. Connect the sample transfer line to the ion source housing grounding union.

Set up the calibration probe

1. Replace H-ESI probe to calibration probe (grey).
2. Replace the red transfer line between grounding union and calibration probe to grey transfer line (dedicated for calibration).
3. Adjust the position of probe at position 1 for the syringe flow rate 3-5 µl/min, the height between the L and M and left-to right position in center.

Apply the favorites settings for the calibration process

1. In the Thermo MS Tuning window, MS is in **Standby** mode, see **Table 1**.
2. In the data type list and change from **Centroid** to the **Profile** data type.
3. Click the **Define Scan** tab and select **Full Scan** mode.

Table 1. Data type list

4. Under system settings in the Favorites pane, right-click **H-ESI Default for EMRS Calibration with Positive Polarity** and choose **Apply**. After calibration in positive mode calibrate negative mode. Then click **H-ESI Default for EMRS Calibration with Negative Polarity**.
5. A default parameter setting for the calibration appears at the top of the Favorites pane, see **Table 2**.
6. In the Tune window, turn the **System On**.

Table 2. Source setting for the EMRS using the calibration probe

Parameter	Positive Polarity Mode	Negative Polarity Mode
Spray Voltage (V)	3500	3200
Sheath Gas (Arb)	0	0
Aux Gas (Arb)	0	0
Sweep Gas (Arb)	0	0
Ion Transfer Tube Temp (°C)	325	325
Vaporizer Temperature (°C)	Parameter not available with ESI	Parameter not available with ESI
Source Fragmentation (V)	30	30
Syringe pump flow rate (µl/min)	2 to 5	2 to 5

Start the flow of calibration solution to the ion source

1. In Tune window right-click on arrow at the right of the Syringe On/Off control. In the Volume list elect 500 µl. In the Flow Rate select 3 µl/min. Click **Apply**.
2. Click Syringe Off to turn syringe pump On. The button changes to **Syringe On**.
3. If necessary, click **Prime** to prime the syringe and tubing at 100 µl/min for a 3 to 5 seconds.
4. Then decrease the flow to 3 µl/min.
5. Let the system equilibrate for 15 minutes.
6. Inspect the spectrum in the spectrum view of the Tune window.
7. For positive mode, check peaks at the following m/z values 69, 102, 215, 622, 922, and 1522, see **Table 3**.

- For negative mode, check peaks with m/z values 69, 113, 302, 602, 1034, and 1634, see **Table 4**.

Table 3. Mass spectral peaks $[M+H]^+$ for EMRS in the positive mode

Component	Positive mode (m/z)
Imidazole	69.04
Triethylamine	102.13
1,8-Bis(diethylamino)naphthalene	215.15
Hexakis(2,2-difluoroethoxy)phosphazene	622.03
Hexakis(2,2,3,3-tetrafluoropropoxy)phosphazene	922.01
Hexakis(1h,1h,5h-octafluoropentoxy)phosphazene	1521.97

Table 4. Mass spectral peaks for EMRS in the negative mode

Component	Negative mode (m/z)
Fragment of TFA	69.00
Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA)	112.99
2,4,6-Tris(trifluoromethyl)-1,3,5-triazine	302.00
2,4,6-Tris(heptafluoropropyl)-1,3,5-triazine $[M+OH]^-$	601.98
Hexakis(2,2,3,3-tertafloropropoxy) phosphazen $[M+TFA]^-$	1033.99
Hexakis(1h,1h,5h-octafluoropentosy) phosphazene $[M+TFA]^-$	1633.95

Evaluation of spray stability

- Click the **Define Scan** tab and select parameters shown in **Table 5**.
- Click **Apply**.

Table 5. SIM scan parameters

Define Scan	
Scan type	SIM scan (Q1)
Q1 Resolution (FWHM)	0.7
Scan Rate (Da/sec)	250
Scan Width (m/z)	10
CID Gas (mTorr)	0
Use Calibrated RF Lens	yes
Source Fragmentation (V)	30
Q1 SIM Scan Table	
Precursor m/z	622 (602 in Negative Mode)

- Click the **Plot Chromatogram** icon at the lower right of the Thermo MS Tuning window. The Plot Chromatogram dialog box open, see **Table 6**.
- Select the **Spray Stability** check box and the **User Defined m/z** option.
- In the mass table, type 622 (602 in negative mode) in the mass column of row 1.

6. Click **Ok**. And The Spray stability check begins.
7. The %RSD plot displays the calculated results.

Table 6. Thermo MS Tuning window

8. You can observe the signal stability and the effects of changes to various parameters in the chromatogram and spectrum plot.
9. You can observe a real-time graph of the RSD for a 10Da-select ion monitoring scan that is centered around mass defined in the m/z 622 (602 in negative mode).
10. Observe the RSD graph and review the signal stability and RSD value.
11. Maximum RSD (threshold) is **10%** and **Excellent or Good** signal stability.
12. If the signal stability is Poor: ensure the proper installation of sweep cone, make adjustment of the API probe (forward/back, depth), increase, or decrease spray voltage (do not exceed 3.6 kV), adjust sheath gas (positive mode 0 – 4, negative mode 0 - 5, but it is usually either 0 or between 4-5), adjust the flow rate of calibration solution.
13. Once the spray stability is achieved, and it is stable, select **Full Scan** mode and start the **System Check** or the **System Calibration**.

Run the automated System Calibration routine

1. Click the **Calibration** tab and select the **System Calibration** option.
2. Click **Start**.
3. When the calibration is completed, the Tune application prompts you to generate a report of the calibration result. Select **Generate Report Now**. Click **Ok**.

4. Save to folder **Reports**.
C:\Thermo\Instruments\Reports
5. After the MS completes the calibration procedure in positive mode, run the calibration routine in negative mode.

Automated System Check routine

1. The **System Check** option is not available if the Calibration is expired.
2. Click the Calibration tab and select the **System Check** option.
3. Click **Start**.
4. When the calibration is completed, **Generate Report Now**.
5. Click **Ok**.

Automated System Calibration done

1. In the Tune window, MS turn into **Standby** mode.
2. Turn on the Syringe pump.
3. Trash the rest of **Calibration Solution**. It is not recommended to use the rest again.
4. Wash the syringe with 50% acetonitrile and store in box.
5. Unmount the grey transfer line and store in box.
6. Place H-ESI probe for analysis.